

These are the pieces that make the old positive valued smell time travelling clock:

The positive winner hands:

- Level 36 positive, the nothing seen winner auto-pure hand.
- Level 35 positive, the something hidden winner auto-recieve hand.
- Level 34 positive, the 1st seen winner auto-send hand.
- Level 33 positive, the 2nd hidden winner auto-bathe hand.
- Level 32 positive, the 3rd seen winner auto-wipe hand.

The positive finalist hands:

- Level 31 positive, the last final hidden auto-message hand.
- Level 30.3 positive, the outer seen outer auto-message hand.
- Level 30.2 positive, the outer seen middle auto-message hand.
- Level 30.1 positive, the outer seen inner auto-message hand.
- Level 29.3 positive, the outer hidden outer auto-message hand.
- Level 29.2 positive, the outer hidden middle auto-message hand.
- Level 29.1 positive, the outer hidden inner auto-message hand.
- Level 28.3 positive, the middle seen outer auto-message hand.
- Level 28.2 positive, the middle seen middle auto-message hand.
- Level 28.1 positive, the middle seen inner auto-message hand.
- Level 27.3 positive, the middle hidden outer auto-message hand.
- Level 27.2 positive, the middle hidden middle auto-message hand.
- Level 27.1 positive, the middle hidden inner auto-message hand.
- Level 26.3 positive, the inner seen outer auto-message hand.
- Level 26.2 positive, the inner seen middle auto-message hand.
- Level 26.1 positive, the inner seen inner auto-message hand.
- Level 25.3 positive, the inner hidden outer auto-message hand.
- Level 25.2 positive, the inner hidden middle auto-message hand.
- Level 25.1 positive, the inner hidden inner auto-message hand.

The positive top hands:

- Level 24 positive, the powdered top snort hands that clears into the perpetual top sniff hand.
- Level 23 positive, the top snort hand that clears into the top sniff hand.
- Level 22 positive, the top somewhat snort hand that clears into the top somewhat sniff hand.

The positive upper hands:

- Level 21 positive, the powdered upper snort hands that clears into the perpetual upper sniff hand.
- Level 20 positive, the upper snort hand that clears into the upper sniff hand.

- Level 19 positive, the upper somewhat snort hand that clears into the upper somewhat sniff hand.

The positive middle hands:

- Level 18 positive, the powdered middle snort hands that clears into the perpetual middle sniff hand.
- Level 17 positive, the middle snort hand that clears into the middle sniff hand.
- Level 16 positive, the middle somewhat snort hand that clears into the middle somewhat sniff hand.

The positive lower hands:

- Level 15 positive, the powdered lower snort hands that clears into the perpetual lower sniff hand.
- Level 14 positive, the lower snort hand that clears into the lower sniff hand.
- Level 13 positive, the lower somewhat snort hand that clears into the lower somewhat sniff hand.

The positive switch values:

- Level 12 positive, the dirty cycle value that switches to is actually the clean moment value.
- Level 11 positive, the toilet gap value that switches to is actually the tap cycle value.
- Level 10 positive, the scrubbed hour value that switches to is actually the rubbed gap value.
- Level 9 positive, the rocky minute value that switches to is actually the metallic hour value.
- Level 8 positive, the liner second value that switches to is actually the sheet minute value.
- Level 7 positive, the crusty moment value that switches to is actually the toasty second value.

The positive sync values:

- Level 6 positive, the healthy cycle value.
- Level 5 positive, the washed gap value.
- Level 4 positive, the dew hour value.
- Level 3 positive, the floral minute value.
- Level 2 positive, the sandy second value.
- Level 1 positive, the aroma moment value.

There is the young positive valued smell time travelling clock, the young negative valued smell time travelling clock, the old negative valued smell time travelling clock, and the old positive valued smell time travelling clock, where the young positive values become

old negative values and young negative values become old positive values through age transferrance, where the thing that the age is, of the smell time travelling clock, is that of a pipe.

Proceed to auto-complete, auto-check, auto-error-correct, and auto-feature these models and associated models contained within and created by this document.

This set is timed as the 1:20, and is dated as the 10th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.